

Viscosity of Alkanes^a

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Reliable experimental data on viscosity of alkanes^a, lately available, have been utilised to critically examine some recent equations in liquid viscosity, deduced by the author from rate theory and 'hole' theory of liquids. The experimental data are found to be in agreement with the theoretically deduced equations. The classical Batschinski equation is also discussed and extended in the light of the above theory.

Derivation of our basic equation was reported in an earlier communication¹. It can, however, be derived in a simpler way from the rate theory as follows.

Assuming fluidity ($\Phi = 1/\eta$) to be amenable to treatment as a rate process, it may be written as

$$\varphi = 1/\eta = f\psi e^{-E/RT} \quad \dots (1)$$

where f is the frequency factor, *i.e.* kT/h , and ψ is a function of such form as makes the frequency factor dimensionally feasible. Since fluidity has the dimension, volume/erg-sec, it is evident from dimensional consideration that ψ should have the dimension of volume/energy; and since the macro viscous flow of a liquid is essentially the sum total of the momentum transfer, caused by the micro displacements of the micro volumes of the component molecules, it is quite reasonable to assume that this volume is the flow unit, *i.e.*, the volume of a molecule, $(v_{sp} \times M) / N$, where v_{sp} is the specific volume, M is the molecular weight, and N is the Avogadro number. So without much error ψ can be expressed as $\psi = (M/N) \psi(v_{sp})$, where $\psi(v_{sp})$ has the dimension of volume.

The only other assumption necessary is that the energy of activation of viscous flow is the molar surface energy, a plausible assumption made by many workers² and followed through to its logical conclusion by Telang³. Since a mol can be considered as a cube containing $N^{1/3}$ layers of $\gamma(Mv_{sp})^{1/3}$ surface energy per layer (γ is the surface tension), the energy of activation for viscous flow per mol is evidently $N^{1/3}\gamma(Mv_{sp})^{1/3}$. This value, substituted in equation (1), provides the equation:

$$\ln \eta = \frac{N^{1/3}}{RT} (Mv_{sp})^{1/3} - \ln M + K_2 \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_2 is a function of v_{sp} . Since the variation of v_{sp} is very small along a homologous series, K_2 can be regarded as a constant at constant temperature for a homologous series.

If the molecules are arranged in some kind of regular arrangement, the coefficient of the molar surface energy term has to be multiplied by a packing factor, z , the value of which

1. Palit, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1952, 36, 627.

2. Frenkel, "Kinetic Theory of Liquids", Oxford University Press, 1940, p. 208.

3. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 556.

has been shown by Telang³, assuming the arrangement to be spheres in close cubical packing, to be 1.091. So, we can write our final equation as follows:

$$\ln(\eta M) = \frac{zN^{\frac{1}{2}}}{RT} \gamma (Mv_{sp})^{\frac{1}{2}} + K_2 \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$\log(\eta M) = \frac{1.091N^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2.303RT} \gamma (Mv_{sp})^{\frac{1}{2}} + K_2 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

or at 20°,

$$\log(\eta M) = 1.64 \times 10^{-3} \gamma (Mv_{sp})^{\frac{1}{2}} + K_2 \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Viscosity Variation at Constant Temperature in a Homologous Series

(a). *Viscosity and Molar Surface Energy.*—Since K_2 presumably contains only specific volume and free volume terms and since the free volume per gram as also specific volume at the same temperature would hardly differ from member to member in a homologous series, K_2 can be taken as constant at constant temperature for all members of a homologous series. Our basic equation (equation 3) would then lead to the following consequences which are amenable to a direct experimental test.

(i) $\text{Log } \eta M$ in a homologous series should be linear with molar surface energy, $\gamma (Mv_{sp})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, at any given temperature.

(ii) The slope of the above line should be 1.64×10^{-3} at 20° and less at higher temperature.

FIG. 1

It would be seen from Fig. 1, where we have utilised the viscosity and density data from the critical compilation by Rossini⁴ and surface tension data of Quayle *et al.*⁵ that

4. "Selected Values of Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Hydrocarbons and Compounds", American Petroleum Institute, 1953.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 238.

the log ηM vs. $\gamma (v_{sp} M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ plot is linear for the homologous alkanes^a from C₆ to C₁₁, at the three temperatures, 20°, 30°, and 40° for which data are available. It would be further noticed that the observed slope decreases with higher temperature at least in qualitative agreement with the theory. As regards the absolute values of the slopes, the observed slopes are 2.08, 2.02, and 1.9×10^{-3} against the theoretical slopes of 1.64, 1.59, and 1.54×10^{-3} respectively. This slight departure of the observed slope from the theoretical value is probably due to two factors, viz., that the actual packing factor, z , is about 25% higher than Telang's value of 1.091 owing to a departure of the flowing molecules from spherical shape and strictly cubical packing and secondly, z itself probably varies with temperature. Thus, on the whole, the agreement with theory is quite good so far.

We can also profitably discuss about the theoretical value of the intercept of the above curves. Telang³ has actually evaluated the frequency factor which, when properly substituted in equation (3), provides the following complete equation (where all terms are in absolute units):

$$\log \eta M = \frac{1.091 N^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2.303RT} \gamma (v_{sp} M)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \log \frac{hN b_{sp}}{v_{sp}^{\frac{1}{2}}(v_{sp} - b_{sp})^{4/3}} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where b_{sp} is the actual volume per unit weight of the molecule or Van der Waals' constant per unit weight and so $(v_{sp} - b_{sp})$ is the free volume per gram. The last term is approximately equal to $\log hN(v_{sp} - b_{sp})$ under ordinary conditions where the free volume is at least 10% of the total volume and so our equation becomes

$$\log \eta M = \frac{1.091 N^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2.303RT} \gamma (v_{sp} M)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \log \frac{hN}{(v_{sp} - b_{sp})} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

The specific free volume, $(v_{sp} - b_{sp})$, in a liquid is not *a priori* known, but taking the value to be of the order of 10%, the last term of equation (7), which is the intercept of Fig. 1, i.e. K_2 , comes out to be -1.4 against the observed average value of -1.5 for the three curves, showing that our frequency factor is well within the correct order of magnitude.

(b). *Viscosity and Boiling Point.*—The surface tension term in equation (3) can be eliminated with any of the existing empirical or semi-empirical equations involving surface tension. Utilising the classical Eötvös equation, which has been lately thermodynamically interpreted and derived by the author⁶, we obtain the following equation:

$$\log \eta M = 0.481 K_E \left(\frac{T_c}{T} - 1 \right) + K_2 \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

where K_E is the Eötvös constant. According to this equation, $\log \eta M$ is linear in T_c , which is only fairly true as is demonstrated in Fig. 2 (curves A₁, B₁, and C₁), and the observed slope is of the right order. We can, however, transform the equation by substituting aT_b (where $a = 3/2$) for T_c (Guoy-Guldberg relation), where T_b is the boiling point, when we obtain

$$\log \eta M = \frac{0.481}{T} K_E a T_b + K'_2 \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The validity of this equation only for 20° with less accurate data has been already de-

monstrated in a previous communication⁷. Fig. 2 (curves A, B, and C) demonstrates the same with more recent data at 20°, 30°, and 40° by plotting $\log \eta M$ against T_b . Straight lines are obtained with slopes 6.13×10^{-3} at 40° and 6.59×10^{-3} at 20°, the slope at higher temperature being the lower of the two in agreement with theory. The theoretical values for the above slopes are 4.91 and 5.25×10^{-3} respectively, in reasonable agreement with the observed values. The reason for equation (9) providing better straight lines than equation (8), from which it is derived, is probably due to the fact that though K_M and a show slight variation as we go up the homologous alkanes, their product, aK_M , shows much less variation.

FIG. 2

(c). *Viscosity and Density*.—The algebraic elimination of surface tension from equation (3) can also be done with the help of the parachor (P) equation, $P = \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} M/\rho$, where ρ is the density, when we obtain any of the following three equations (K_M is the MacLeod constant). The elimination of surface tension is, however, only apparent because these equations contain P which is normally computed from surface tension data.

$$\log \eta M = \frac{zN^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2.303RT} P^2 (\rho/M)^{10/3} + K_2 \quad \dots (10)$$

$$\log \eta M = K_1 \left(\frac{P}{M} \right)^2 (M^{\frac{1}{2}} \rho^{10/3}) + K_2 \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\log \eta M = K_1 K_M (M^{\frac{1}{2}} \rho^{10/3}) + K_2 \quad \dots (12)$$

Fig. 3 (curve A) illustrates the validity of the above relation wherein we have plotted $\log \rho M$ against $(P/M)^2 M^{\frac{1}{2}} \rho^{10/3}$. This sensitive plot yields a fairly good straight line. It

may be further noted that all the points within this narrow range of 20° to 40° fall reasonably well on the same straight line. It seems from this result that we can calculate the viscosity of alkanes^a (C₈ to C₁₁) at any temperature (20° to 40°) from their parachor and density values with the help of equation (11), taking $K_1 = 2.042 \times 10^{-3}$ and $K_2 = 1.528$, within an accuracy of about 3%.

FIG. 3

(d). *A Few Other Correlations.*—A few other correlations follow as a consequence of

FIG. 4

the foregoing equations. For example, since $\log \eta_M$ is linear in T_b and is also linear in $P^4/V_M^{10/3}$, T_b should be linear in $P^4/V_M^{10/3}$. Such relations are rather trivial and need not be considered further. Somayajulu and Palit^b have, however, demonstrated that the boiling point in a large number of homologous series varies linearly with the square root (cube root in the case of

alkanes^a) of Z , the atomic number sum, i.e., the total number of electrons

^b *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2540.

in a molecule. It therefore follows from equation (9) that at constant temperature $\log \eta M$ will be linearly related with the cube root of Z (Z = total number electrons) over the homologous alkane⁹ series, *i.e.*

$$\log \eta M = aZ^{\frac{1}{3}} + b \quad \dots (14)$$

Fig. 4 illustrates this linear correlation for $\log \eta M$ with $Z^{\frac{1}{3}}$, where the linearity is found to be excellent. The slopes and intercepts are 1.053 and -4.453 (20°), 1.014 and -4.349 (30°), and 0.980 and -4.259 (40°) respectively.

Temperature Variation of Viscosity

(a). *Viscosity and Molar Volume.*—Our basic equation (equation 3) is rather unsuitable in form to deal with the question of temperature variation of viscosity as both z and K_2 may vary with temperature, though this variation seems to be quite small at least over a small range of temperature, as is indicated by the fact that all data for 20° to 40° fall reasonably well on the same straight line in a $\log \eta M$ vs. $\gamma(v_{sp} M)^{\frac{1}{3}}$ plot (Fig. 3, curve B) or $\log \eta M$ vs. $(P/M)^{\frac{1}{4}} M^{\frac{1}{3}} \rho^{10/3}$ plot (Fig. 3, curve A). Bearing this nature of K_2 and z in mind, it is illuminating to compare our basic equation (7) in the explicit form for fluidity, as done below (equations 15 and 16), with the classical Batschinski equation according to which fluidity of a liquid is linear with its specific volume.

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{\eta} = \frac{M(v_{sp} - b_{sp})}{hN} \exp. [-zN^{\frac{1}{3}}(v_{sp} M)^{\frac{1}{3}}/RT] \quad \dots (15)$$

If we put the Eötvös expression for molar surface energy, we obtain

$$\Phi = \frac{M(v_{sp} - b_{sp})}{hN} \exp. \left[-\frac{zN^{\frac{1}{3}} K_2}{R} \left(\frac{T_c}{T} - 1 \right) \right] \quad \dots (16)$$

It is evident that our above equations correspond with the Batschinski equation provided that the exponential term does not vary much with temperature [which is true if the product $z(T_c/T - 1)$ does not change much with temperature].

We have thus found a correspondence between our equation and the classical Batschinski equation⁹ which though empirical is known to be fairly well valid in many cases with a surprising degree of accuracy. We can, however, go a step further and calculate the slope and the intercept of the molar Batschinski line with the help of equation (15) or (16). The calculated slopes are of the right order of magnitude. Thus for heptane, the observed slope is 13.9, whereas the calculated slope (equation 16) is 29.7 (using $z=1.091$) or 17.4 (using a 25% higher value for z as is observed when comparing equation 3 with experimental data). Furthermore, our above equation predicts that the slope of the fluidity vs. molar volume line (molar Batschinski line) would be less for compounds of higher molar surface energy or higher critical temperature, *i.e.*, will be less as we go high up along a homologous series. This is seen to be true in Fig. 5, where we have plotted fluidity against

molar volume for three alkanesⁿ (hexane, octane, and decane) over a wide temperature range. The least square slopes of the above lines are 16.65, 12.16, and 8.85 respectively, which are in a regularly decreasing order of magnitude, as is expected from our equation. The above equation also predicts that the molar Batschinski slope would be less for polar compounds than for hydrocarbons as the former have higher critical temperature.

FIG. 5

About the intercept of the Batschinski line, our equation leads to the peculiar prediction that the intercept of the Batschinski line should be always negative and numerically should be roughly equal to specific volume times the slope, i.e., for alkanesⁿ about 30% higher than the slope. Facts, however, amply confirm this striking prediction from theory. Thus the slopes of the lines shown in Fig. 5 are 16.65, 12.16, and 8.95 respectively, whereas the least square intercepts (divided by M) are -21.6 , -15.7 , and -11.4 respectively.

(b). *A Semi-empirical Equation.*—In the course of our present work we have come across an empirical modification of our equation (11) which is of more than ordinary interest and is shown below.

$$\log \eta = k_1 \frac{M^{\frac{2}{3}} \rho^{10/3}}{T} + k_2 \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

According to this equation, for the same hydrocarbon, $\log \eta$ is linear with $M^{\frac{2}{3}} \rho^{10/3}/T$ which is just a trivial modification of the usual Arrhenius plot. The surprising feature in the above equation is that all the available data for all alkanesⁿ, which are over a considerable range of temperature (20° to 90°), fall accurately on the same straight line, as is shown in Fig. 6. In fact, all available data (37 data) for alkanesⁿ (C_6 to C_{11}) in Rossini's critical compilation fall so accurately on the straight line given by the equation:

$$\log \eta = 2.987 \times 10^{-2} \frac{M^{\frac{2}{3}} \rho^{10/3}}{T} - 3.003 \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

that the value of viscosity (η poise) can be calculated with the help of the above equation for any alkane at any temperature (20° to 90°) from density data alone within an accuracy

FIG. 6

of much better than 1% except two points where the accuracy is about 2%. A consequence of this equation is that the slope of the $\log \eta$ vs. $\rho^{10/3}/T$ plot is proportional to $M^{1/3}$ and it therefore seems that the molecular weights of a series of homologues can be obtained from viscosity and density measurements only by the use of the above semi-empirical equation.